

TABLE 1

Sr. No.	Complex	% Co(II)	Analysis % N	Mol. wt.	μ_{eff} (B.M.)	λ_{max} (nm)
1.	[Co(II) (Pyr) ₂ · 2H ₂ O]	22.29 (22.14)	10.32(10.68)	—	4.45	—
2.	[Co(II) (Pyr) ₂ endn]	20.12 (20.05)	19.32(19.50)	304 (287)	4.69	430 (E = 14.64), 560, 835
3.	[Co(II) (Pyr) ₂ pndn]	19.28 (19.40)	09.59(09.30)	309 (302)	4.70	435 (E = 17.22), 560, 740

Calculated values are in parantheses.

TABLE 2—(INFRA RED ASSIGNMENTS)

	endn	pndn	[Co(II) (Pyr) ₂ endn]	[Co(II) (Pyr) ₂ pndn]
N-H Stretch	3505 msp	3495 mbr	3440 mbr	3375 sbr
N-H bending	1655 msp	1650 msp	1635 mbr	1625 wbr
C-N Stretch	1225 ssp	1215 msp	1155 msp	1140 ssp
C = O Stretch	—	—	1590 mbr	1625 mbr

Abbreviation : endn = ethylenediamine, pndn = propylenediamine, pyr = 2-pyrrolidone, m = medium, s = strong, sp = sharp, br = broad.

frequency remains unaltered on coordination ; on the other hand the N-H bending vibration which usually occurs in the range 1500–1590 cm⁻¹ disappears on coordination, indicating that the coordination take place through nitrogen atom only.

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Flavonoid Constituents of *Lycopersicon esculentum*

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LYCOSPERSICON esculentum belongs to the family Solanaceae and is rich in vitamins A and C¹.

The defatted seeds of *L. esculentum* were first extracted with acidulated (1 N HCl) methanol and the study of the methanolic extract containing anthocyanins has already been communicated. Thereafter the seeds were extracted with cold acetone. The acetone extract after concentration under reduced pressure was treated with ether and the ethereal extract on concentration yielded a yellow solid mass which on paper chromatography and TLC

examination showed the presence of two ferric positive spots. The yellow solid mass was chromatographed on a column of silica gel and eluted with benzene : ethylacetate [(i) (75 : 25, V/V), (ii) (15 : 85, V/V)]. The eluate (i) gave compound X and eluate (ii) gave compound Y respectively.

Compound X was crystallised from a mixture of acetone : methanol (1 : 1), when light yellow crystals, m.p. 316°, C, 59.58; H, 3.33%, m/e = 302, molecular formula C₁₅H₁₀O₇, acetyl derivative, m.p. 198°–99°, were obtained. Co-chromatographic examination and mixed m.p. determination with authentic sample of quercetin confirmed it to be quercetin.

Compound Y crystallised from methanol (m.p. 274°–75°), responded to usual colour tests for flavonoids. It gave no positive Molisch's test indicating it to be a free flavone and not a glycoside. It was identified as Kaempferol by co-chromatography, mixed m.p. determination and superimposable spectral studies.

References

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A Study of the Complex Compounds of N-Benzenesulphonyl Glycine with some Metal Ions. Part XXI. Cu(II) and Hg(II) Chelates of N-Benzenesulphonyl L(–) Aspartic Acid and N-Benzenesulphonyl L(+) Glutamic Acid

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IN a previous communication¹, complex compounds formed by the ligand N-benzenesulphonyl L(–) aspartic acid (R₂H₂) have been reported. Now a